

STAGES OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL
INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: Social institutions are important in shaping human behavior and maintaining social order. These institutions, including the family, education, religion, economy, and government, have evolved to meet the needs of individuals and communities. This article examines the stages of formation and development of social institutions, highlighting their evolution from simple structures to complex systems that affect all aspects of social life. The discussion focuses on how these institutions emerge, grow, adapt and change in response to social, cultural, economic and political changes. Understanding these stages is essential for analyzing the dynamics of social interactions and the factors that contribute to the stability and development of societies.

Keywords: Social institutions, formation, development, evolution, family, education, religion, economy, state, social order.

Introduction. Social institutions are the main structures of society, they organize and regulate human activities, and they ensure that individuals and groups act in an orderly and predictable manner. These institutions evolve at distinct stages of formation and development, reflecting the needs, values, and norms of the communities they serve. Understanding these stages helps us understand how institutions influence social behavior, maintain order, and adapt to changing circumstances over time. [1]

Stages of formation of social institutions. The formation of social institutions can be divided into several stages, each of which represents a stage of evolution from informal social practices to formal structures that affect all levels of society.

Exit stage. The seeds of the social institution are the stage of emergence of the planted place. It begins with informal social practices or traditions that develop in response to specific needs or problems within a society. [2]

For example, when the institution of the family arose from the need for mutual support, reproduction and raising children, religious customs arose as a result of humanity's desire to understand natural phenomena, to seek spiritual guidance.

The stage of setting norms. These practices become more consistent and become norms that govern behavior within society. At this stage, rules, traditions and Customs begin to form around these practices, and they form the basis for optimal behavior.

Norms are strengthened through repeated social interactions, legitimacy and acceptance within a group, leading to a general understanding of roles and expectations.

Institutionalization stage. In the institutionalization phase, established norms become formal structures recognized by the wider society. This stage involves codifying practices into laws, regulations or formal guidelines that define the functions and roles of the institution.

For example, legal systems and the development of educational curricula reflect this stage as society formally organizes these functions to ensure consistency and stability. [3]

Stages of development of social institutions. Once established, social institutions undergo a continuous process of development to adapt to changing

social conditions, technological progress, and cultural shifts. This development can be divided into the following stages:

The stage of growth and expansion. At this stage, social institutions expand their influence and adapt their structures to meet the growing needs of society. They can diversify their functions, introduce new roles and change existing norms to better serve society.

For example, the economy as a social institution has grown from a simple system of exchange to complex global markets, reflecting an increase in the scale of production, trade, and technological innovation.[4]

Adaptation and transformation stage. Institutions must adapt to internal and external pressures such as social movements, technological advances, and political changes. This phase is characterized by changes in policies, practices and objectives to remain relevant and effective in a changing world.

For example, the education system has been transformed to include digital learning platforms and updated curricula to meet the demands of the modern workforce and knowledge-based economy.

The stage of rejection or reinvention. Social institutions can go into decline when they cannot adapt to changing social needs or their tasks are taken over by new institutions. This phase can lead to the demise of the institution or its reinvention in a new form.

For example, while traditional religious institutions have been in decline in some regions due to secularization, in other regions they have reinvented themselves to adapt to modern values and social problems.

Factors affecting the development of social institutions. Several factors play a decisive role in the development of social institutions:

Cultural values and beliefs. Cultural values and beliefs strongly influence the development of institutions, as they determine what is considered important or

acceptable in society. Institutions are formed on the basis of dominant ideologies, traditions and collective consciousness of the people.

Technological advances. Technology has a significant impact on the development of social institutions, changing their relationship with performance and society.[5] advances in communication, transport and Information Technology have led to the globalization of institutions, making them interconnected and more efficient.

Economic and political changes. Economic changes, such as industrialization or globalization and political changes, such as revolutions or policy reforms, can dramatically change the structure and role of institutions. For example, the transition from a feudal economy to a capitalist market changed economic and political institutions around the world.

Social movements and conflicts. Social movements and conflicts often serve as catalysts for institutional change. Demands for equality, human rights and social justice can lead to significant changes in laws, policies and societal norms, reshaping institutions to better reflect contemporary values.[6]

Conclusion. The formation and development of social institutions are dynamic processes that play a decisive role in the evolution of society. These institutions go through stages of emergence, growth, adaptation, and possible decline or reinvention to adapt to the changing needs of their communities. Understanding these stages provides valuable insights into the complex interactions between social forces and institutional structures. As societies continue to develop, the flexibility and robustness of social institutions remain important to strengthen stability, progress, and social cohesion.

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